

Fig. 3 shows the distribution of algorithm types based on functional similarity.



Fig. 3 Distribution of algorithm type based on function similarity



Fig. 3-1. Distribution of Distance-based methods and Regression Algorithms



Fig. 3-2. Distribution of Decision Tree and Bayesian Algorithms



Fig. 3-3. Distribution of Kernel Methods and Associated Role Learning



Fig. 3-4. Distribution of Ensemble Methods and Artificial Neural Networks